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Family Violence As A Predictor Of Aggressive Behaviours Among In-School Adolescents In Anambra State

*Okoyezu Vivian Ukamaka Prof. Obikeze J, Nnamdi & Prof. M,C Okonkwo

Department of Educational Foundations,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria
*E-mail: vivianlinus20@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examined the predictive value of family violence on aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The literature was reviewed under the following sub-headings; conceptual, theoretical, empirical studies and summary of literature reviewed. The study adopted correlational research design. Population of the students comprised 20,560 SSII in-school adolescents in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of the study consisted of 347 students drawn using Taro Yamane formular. Multistage sampling technique was used to draw the sample. Child Exposure to Domestic Violence Scale (CEDV) and Aggression Questionnaire (AQ) were adapted as instruments for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and content validation. The reliability of the instruments were established using Cronbach Alpha. The computation yielded coefficient values of 0.84, and 0.82 for CEDV and AQ respectively. The researcher administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of six research assistants. Simple regression analyses was used to answer research questions 1 and 2 and tested hypotheses 1 and 2. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that family violence has a strong positive predictive value ($\beta = 0.56$, $t = 12.61$, $p = 0.000$) on aggressive behaviours. The findings also showed that Family violence has strong positive predictive value ($\beta = 0.57$, $t = 9.03$, $p = 0.000$) ($\beta = 0.56$, $t = 8.89$, $p = 0.000$) on aggressive behaviours of male and female adolescents with slightly more variance among males compared to the females. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Educational Psychologists and school administrators should provide opportunities to counselling services, support groups, and hotlines for adolescents affected by family violence as well as training on life skills, such as conflict resolution, communication, and problem-solving.

Keywords: Family Violence, Aggressive Behaviours, Gender and In-school Adolescents

INTRODUCTION

Education is the cornerstone of human development and societal progress. It serves as a tool for personal and societal advancement, equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to navigate life successfully. Schools are designed to provide spaces where students feel safe, respected, and supported. The Nigerian educational system, guided by policy objectives, aims to raise the quality of education and position it as a driver of national development (Ugochukwu et al., 2021). However, the persistent prevalence of aggressive behaviours undermines these goals. Instead of being sanctuaries of safety and growth, schools have become arenas for hostility, particularly aggression, which significantly

compromise the quality of education and the safety of school environments with many students facing intimidation and violence, often leading to absenteeism, fear, and academic underperformance.

Aggressive behaviour is a range of actions or attitudes that are intended to cause harm, discomfort or intimidation to others. It also includes behaviour aimed at achieving dominance, control or retaliation in response to perceived threats or frustrations. In their views, Peng et al (2018), it is referred to as hostile actions intended to hurt someone or establish dominance. For the purpose of this study, aggressive behaviour is described by the researcher as actions that are intended to cause harm or injury to another person, either physically or psychologically. This includes a wide range of behaviours, from overt physical acts such as hitting, kicking, or pushing, to more covert psychological acts like yelling, insults, social exclusion, use of harsh language, or spreading rumors. It is characterized by the deliberate desire to inflict harm or discomfort on the target.

Aggressive behaviour is a complex topic that encompasses various forms of assertiveness and hostility. Shekarey et al, (2020) contended that aggressive behaviours are common in secondary schools and aggressive behaviour among the students is an issue of concern among stakeholders in education essentially because schools are institutions designed for teaching and learning. Aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents can be categorized into four groups namely, physical, verbal, relational and cyberbullying (Rigby, 2018). Physical aggression is hostile form of aggression. Its aim is to cause bodily damage. It includes kicking, pushing, shoving, fighting, hitting, slapping, among others. Verbal aggression involves the use of words to hurt or threaten others. It includes name-calling, teasing or making derogatory comments. Relational aggression involves harming others through damage to relationships or social status. It can include spreading rumours, excluding others from social activities, or manipulating friendships. Cyberbullying involves using digital space or technologies, such as social media or text messaging to harm or threaten others. This behaviour is very complicated with a variety of multidimensional causes such as exposure to aggressive role model, frustrations, negative social relations with peers and teachers at school, peer pressure, low self-esteem among others. However, Amuda-Kannike (2018) revealed that biological factors can cause aggressive behaviours among secondary school students. These factors are brain dysfunction (poor functioning of the frontal and temporal region of the brain), birth complications, nutrition deficiency, genetics, stress and drug abuse. Aggressive behaviours can cause many negative impact for the victim as well as the perpetrator. Kuar and Kuar (2020) noted that students who are victims of aggressive behaviour experience depression, low self-esteem, anxiety, stress, headache, sleep difficulties, problems meeting school's academic demands and the desire to skip school. Furthermore, UNESCO (2021) acknowledged that aggressive behaviour had an impact on the ability of students to get to and from school, to learn effectively while in school, to remain in school long enough to reap the benefits of education, and in extreme cases, school aggression may result in death.

The prevalence of aggressive behaviours in the form of bullying in schools has become more prominent in the last few years, as news, articles about aggressive behaviour within the school setting is now on the increase (APA 2021). On their part, Obikeze and Obi (2020) stressed how this ugly development has adversely affected the academic performance of the students and their overall wellbeing, and how students continued involvement in aggressive behaviour has brought miseries and anguish to many parents, teachers, psychologists, guidance counsellors and the government despite many strategies put in place to curb it, the problem persists. Therefore, the mantra that school is perceived to be a place where students should feel safe and secure is no longer valid and the reality is that significant number of students are the target of aggressive acts. Therefore, it becomes necessary to explore some factors that may predict the behaviour of the perpetrators of aggressive behaviours in schools. Although aggressive behaviour is a widespread phenomenon, the focus of this study is to determine whether a relationship exists between family violence and aggressive behaviour. In other words, could family violence predict aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State? By examining the correlation between family violence and aggressive behaviours, this study sought to provide valuable insights into the intricate web of influences shaping adolescent behaviour in this specific Nigerian context.

Family violence is a worldwide problem with series of long-term adverse consequences for survivors, especially children, across their life span. It is a common occurrence, with 37.3% of youth endorsing physical assault by peers or siblings and 15.2% endorsing maltreatment within the past year (Finkelhor et al. 2015). It is an act or acts of violence or abuse within a family. Family violence is any form of abusive behaviour which is physical, emotional, sexual, or psychological that occurs within a family or domestic setting. It involves one family member exerting control, harm, or intimidation over another, often creating a cycle of fear and power imbalance. The World Health Organization (2021) defines family violence as "the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against a family member, or against a former family member, or in a close relationship (excluding situations of armed conflict)" and has identified children as the most common victims of family violence. Apeh and Bernice (2020) views family violence as violence between parents, violence between siblings, violence between parents and the child as well as negative parental disciplinary actions. In the interest of this study, family violence is referred to by the researcher as any form of abuse, mistreatment or neglect that occurs among family members. It is an absence of harmony in the family.

Family violence can take different forms. Communities and Justice (2019) identified the following forms of family violence as physical abuse, psychological abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, religious abuse and financial abuse. Kallstrom et al, (2022) found different patterns of abuse based on the perpetrators. Parents were most likely to use physical abuse, emotional abuse and sexual abuse, whereas siblings typically perpetrated property crimes and partners committed sexual assault. Peers were the most likely perpetrators of both physical and verbal abuse. Exposure to family violence including physical, emotional, or psychological harm, can intensify the development of aggressive behaviours (Xia et al., 2018). The prevalence of regular, intense conflicts in the family and lack of affective stability among the family members are among the risk factors reported in adolescents as potential precursors for the development of aggressive behaviours. Ismeli (2022) contended that adolescents exposed to family violence may have a higher tendency to accept violent norms that legitimize the use of violence as a means to resolve personal and interpersonal problems. In the same vein, Apeh and Bernice (2020) asserted that adolescents who have experienced family violence are more likely to develop depression, anxiety and a range of other emotional problems that are related to antisocial behaviours such as aggressive behaviour.

Exposure to family violence negatively impacts on the students which is reflected in high levels of physical, social, and psychological problems. Jaffe et al (as cited in Ogazie & Ajoku, 2024) revealed that some of the negative traits these students display include aggressive behaviour, reduction of social competence, cultural activities, depression, anxiety disorder, phobias, low self-concept, engaging in substance intake, learning problems among others. In the same vein, Apeh and Bernice (2020) noted that family violence can lead to anxiety, depression, irregular school attendance due to physical injuries or emotional distress, aggressive behaviour, substance abuse, truancy, social isolation among others. In contrast, adolescents from non-violent families are more likely to experience better psychological well-being. Family environments characterized by non-violence often provide a supportive and nurturing atmosphere, which can buffer adolescents from engaging in aggressive behaviour. There are strong theoretical reasons to expect that this factor, - family violence - play critical role in predicting adolescent aggressive behaviour.

Furthermore, gender differences add another layer of complexity to understanding adolescent aggression. There is ongoing debate surrounding whether aggressive behaviour exhibited by girls differs significantly from or resembles that of boys in similar circumstances. Research suggests a complex relationship between gender and aggressive behaviour in adolescents. Research in gender differences showed that male students scored significantly higher in different dimensions of aggressive behaviours such as physical, verbal, anger and hostility than female students (Afusat, 2024). On the other hand, Snoban and Kumar (2016) contended that female students exhibited more aggressive behaviours than male students. Although a good number of researchers like Ismail (2022) investigated family violence and its relationship to aggressive behaviours among university students, the problem of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents seems to persist and remain a source of worry and concern to many

researchers. This has necessitated this study which sought to investigate family violence as a predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents is an issue of concern among stakeholders in education essentially because schools are institutions designed for teaching and learning. Unarguably, teaching and learning can only successfully take place in a conducive environment devoid of intimidations, harassment, insecurity and fear.

However, the researcher observed that most secondary school students in Anambra State seem to indulge in various forms of aggressive behaviours such as pushing, fighting, teasing, verbal humiliation, slapping, kicking, bullying, name calling, restiveness, physical confrontations, knife attacks among others. Therefore, the mantra that school is perceived to be a place where students should feel safe and secure is no longer valid and the reality is that significant number of students are the target of aggressive acts. Aggressive behaviours can have negative significant impact on teaching and learning, social relationships and overall well-being. Additionally, it can create a negative learning environment making it challenging for students to focus and succeed academically. Furthermore, aggressive behaviours can contribute to increased stress, anxiety levels, depression, and low self-concept among others.

Addressing Students' aggressive behaviour earlier through developing effective coping strategies is crucial to mitigate these negative effects. This has necessitated this study which sought to investigate family violence as a predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State using gender as moderating variable.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine family violence as a predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the predictive value of Family Violence on aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents.
2. Determine the predictive value of Family Violence on aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study would be of great significance to students, teachers, psychologists, guidance counsellors, parents, policy makers and future researchers. The findings of the study would help students gain insights into how family violence impact on their behaviour. Understanding these would help them reflect on their actions and adopt non-aggressive ways of interacting with other students.

The findings of this study would equip teachers with the knowledge to identify warning signs of aggressive behaviours stemming from family issues. This would help teachers to design strategies to reduce aggressive behaviours among students.

The findings of this study would help psychologists uncover how family violence can contribute to aggressive behaviours. This would enable them design effective interventions targeting specific causes of aggressive behaviours such as addressing family violence and teaching students to navigate family issues.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the predictive value of Family violence on aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents?
2. What is the predictive value of Family violence on aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Family violence would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents.
2. Family violence would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Correlational research design was adopted for this study.

Area of the Study

The research was carried out among in-school adolescents in Anambra State, Nigeria. The people of the state are predominantly traders, farmers, civil servants, and entrepreneurs. Anambra State has six education zones namely Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Onitsha, Ogidi, and Otuocha with 267 public secondary schools.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised 20,560 in-school adolescents from senior secondary two (SS2) students (8,775 males and 10,775 females) in the 267 public secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Anambra State (Planning Research and Statistics Department, Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Anambra State Awka, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study was 392 SS2 students drawn from the population of the study. Multistage sampling technique was used for sample size selection. First, three schools were randomly selected from each of the six Education Zones for good representation, making a total of 18 schools. Within each selected school, students were stratified by gender (male/female) to ensure proportional representation. Then simple random sampling technique was used to draw students from the selected schools. Multistage sampling technique was used to ensure that each strata is represented in the sample in a proportion equivalent to its size in the population.

Instrument for Data Collection

Two instruments were used for data collection: Child Exposure To Domestic Violence Scale (CEDV) developed by Edleson et al. (2007). and Aggression Questionnaire (AQ) developed by Buss and Perry (1992).

Validation of the Instrument

The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The research topic, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses and copies of the questionnaire were given to three senior lecturers in Faculty of Education, Chukwumeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State for validation. One in Educational Psychology, one in Guidance and Counsellor and an expert in Measurement and Evaluation. These validates examined the instruments content coverage, suitability of the items and clarity of the language used. The comments, suggestions and recommendations were used to modify the items before the final production.

Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments were trial-tested in a single administration on a representative sample of 30 (15males, 15females) SS2 in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Enugu state was chosen for reliability because both states shared similar educational characteristics. The responses of the respondents were collated to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. This was done using Cronbach Alpha method. The choice of Cronbach Alpha is in line with Stephen (2017) who recommended Cronbach Alpha as a proper statistical tool for determining the internal consistency of an instrument.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher employed direct and immediate retrieval approach upon completion to ensure a high percentage of return with the aid of six research assistants who were briefed on the modalities for administering the instruments in an appropriate and effective way.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed thus: Simple regression statistics was used to answer research questions 1 and 2 and test hypothesis 1 and 2.

RESULTS

The data obtained from the respondents were organized and analyzed thus

Research Question One: *What is the predictive value of family violence on aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis with Family Violence as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	Remark
Constant	28.10	1.93		
Family Violence	0.60	0.05	0.56	Strong positive predictive value
R = 0.56				
R ² =0.32				
Adj.=0.31				

The simple regression result displayed in Table 2 indicated that the regression model R and the R² are 0.60 and 0.56 respectively. This showed that family violence accounts for 32% of the variance in their aggressive behaviour, which indicated a strong fit. The unstandardized Beta coefficient was 0.60 while the standardized beta coefficient (β) was 0.56. The β value indicated that a unit increase in family violence was associated with 0.56 unit increase in aggressive behaviour amount SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state. This implied that family violence has a strong positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the predictive value of family violence on aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis with Family Violence as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	Remark
Male (n= 171)				
Constant	30.01	2.50		
Family Violence	0.56	0.06	0.57	Strong positive predictive value
R = 0.57				
R ² =0.33				
Adj.=0.32				
Female (n=176)				
Constant	25.98	2.96		
Family Violence	0.65	0.07	0.56	Strong positive predictive value
R = 0.56				
R ² =0.31				
Adj.=0.31				

Table 4 displayed two different simple regression models for male and female SS II in-adolescents with family violence as predictor of aggressive behaviours. For the male sample the model R and R² are 0.57 and 0.33, and 0.56 and 0.31 for the females. This implied that family violence accounts for 33% of the variance in aggressive behaviour among males but explained 31% of the variance among females. These indicated that the regression model fit is strong for both groups. However, the family violence explained slightly more variance in aggressive behaviour among males compared to the females.

The unstandardized and standardized regression coefficients for the males are 0.56 and 0.57 while that of the females were 0.65 and 0.56 respectively. The regression coefficients indicate a unit increase in family violence was associated with 0.57 increase in aggressive behaviour among males and a 0.56 increase in aggressive behaviours among the females.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Family violence would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Table 3: *Test of Significance of Simple Regression Analysis with Family Violence as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)*

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	t	p	Remark
Constant	28.10	1.93		14.60	0.000	Significant
Family Violence	0.60	0.05	0.56	12.61		Significant
R = 0.56						
R ² =0.32						
Adj.=0.31						

Summary of simple regression displayed in Table 7 indicated that family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours of SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state, $\beta = 0.56$, $t = 12.61$, $p = 0.000$. Since the p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This suggests that family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among SS II in-schools adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: Family violence would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Table 4: *Test of Significance of Simple Regression Analysis with Family Violence as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)*

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	t	p	Remark
Male (n= 171)						
Constant	30.01	2.50		12.03	0.000	Significant
Family violence	0.56	0.06	0.57	9.03	0.000	Significant
R = 0.57						
R ² =0.33						
Adj.=0.32						
Female (n=176)						
Constant	25.98	2.96		8.79	0.000	Significant
Family violence	0.65	0.07	0.56	8.89	0.000	Significant
R = 0.56						
R ² =0.31						
Adj.=0.31						

The summary of simple regression displayed in Table 9 showed that family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviour among male SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State, $\beta = 0.57$, $t = 9.03$, $p = 0.000$. In the same vein, family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviour among female SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state, $\beta = 0.56$, $t = 8.89$, $p = 0.000$. Since the p-values were all less than 0.05 level of significant, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that family violence was a significant predictor of

aggressive behaviours among male and female SS II in-schools adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra state.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results of the study, the following findings were found:

1. Family violence has a strong positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Hypothesis two, suggests that family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Family violence has strong positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among male and female SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Hypothesis four implied that family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among male and female SS II in-schools adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings that family violence significantly predicted aggressive behaviours, as indicated by the regression analysis ($\beta = 0.56$, $t = 12.61$, $p = 0.000$), aligned with and extend insights from various empirical studies. Ingram et al. (2020) identified family violence as a catalyst for aggression across multiple contexts, including sibling and peer aggression, ultimately contributing to adverse behavioural outcomes. This supported the present study's conclusion that family violence serves as a foundational predictor of aggressive behaviour, emphasizing its pervasive impact on adolescents' behavioural patterns. The result also coincided with the report of Zhang and Zhang (2021) who found family violence to be a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among adolescents. Their findings showed that adolescents who experienced family violence were more likely to engage in aggressive behaviours. The findings of this study is consistent with Lee and Kim,(2018), Tian et al. (2019), Chaudhry and Shabbir (2018) and Garcia et al, (2020) who observed that there existed a significant positive relationship of family violence on aggressive behaviours of adolescents. Similarly, Kim and Lynch (2015), Ismail (2022) and Izaguire (2018) who found that exposure to family violence predicted increased aggression among adolescents. In the same vein, Agbaria and Natur (2018) found a significant positive correlation between family violence and adolescent aggressive behaviour, highlighting the mediating roles of self-control, social support, and religiosity. While the present study does not focus on mediators, it corroborates the direct link between family violence and aggressive behaviours, suggesting that interventions targeting family environments could reduce aggressive behaviours. Beckmann (2020) also revealed consistent associations between parent-to-child violence and aggression across various social contexts, with the moderating effects of classroom social resources.

The slight variation in the beta values for males ($\beta = 0.57$) and females ($\beta = 0.56$) aligned with Lee and Kim (2018), who reported gender differences in the impact of family violence, with males generally exhibiting slightly higher aggression levels. This may stem from sociocultural expectations or differences in coping mechanisms between genders. Chaudhry and Shabbir (2018) also explored gender-specific effects of family violence, finding males to exhibit higher aggression, while females showed higher levels of pessimism and internalized distress, which might influence their aggressive responses differently. Similarly, Malta et al, (2019) found an association between violence and gender with girls experiencing greater victimization, particularly within unfavourable social and family contexts. Beckmann (2020) emphasized the broader social implications of family violence, demonstrating its consistent associations with aggression in adolescents across various contexts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made.

1. Educational psychologists should educate students on the negative effects of family violence and the importance of healthy family relationships. Support systems, such as counselling services, should be provided to help adolescents affected by family violence.

- 2.. Educational psychologists should educate the teachers on the signs of family violence and aggressive behaviours in adolescents. Teachers can create a safe and supportive classroom environment that promotes positive relationships and reduce aggression. Teachers can refer adolescents who exhibit aggressive behaviours or are affected by family violence to school counsellors or other support services.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, and the discussion, it is concluded that family violence was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among SS II in-school adolescents. Therefore, there is need to address this factor by promoting healthy family relationship, thereby reducing aggressive behaviours and fostering a more supportive academic environment.

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